

Experiences on Gender and Development (GAD) Programs among Teachers: Basis for Designing an Action Plan

Alican M. Pandapatan
Dalipuga National High School,
Iligan City, Lanao del Norte, Philippines

Abstract:- Gender and development (GAD) programs are implemented in different organizations, including the public secondary schools where this study was conducted. Using a cross-sectional survey, the study focused on determining the experiences of 45 teachers on GAD programs and proposed an action plan based on their experiences for better GAD programs implementation. The experiences on GAD programs among teachers were based on the four areas identified in the ASEAN Conference on Civil Service Matters (ACCSM) handbook. These areas include recruitment and selection, performance management, rewards and recognition, and learning and development. Based on their experiences, the teachers perceived the four areas as very important factors in implementing GAD programs. Hence, an action plan was created to realize the importance of addressing issues related to the attainment of full equality and development among men and women teachers in public secondary schools.

Keywords:- development; gender; learning; performance management; recruitment; rewards.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender and development (GAD) program is a development perspective and process that should be considered in the organizations to socially equate the imbalance treatment between men and women [1]. Both sexes are present in most organizations, if not all. The contemporary structure of work organizations is occupied by men and women who are doing the same roles as the counterpart gender. Hence, GAD is described as an approach to addressing men's and women's social differences by creating policies and practices that emphasize the need to challenge the existing gender roles and relations [2].

Ethics is a source of respect and customary practice used to achieve order in an organization [3]. It is suggested that to further assess the relationship of employees' commitment to gender, gender role is prescribed to be included [4]. Since the GAD is part of the programs in every institution, dissecting women's and men's roles in the lens of equality or equity is desired, and growth and development to both sexes would stimulate. Moreover, equity concerns on how to shift the perspective in engaging teachers that align their work within the school environment, the community, and social issues are the challenge to ponder so that goals for achieving equity may meet [5].

The sustainability of employing the practice of GAD is tested in the Philippines during the Covid-19 pandemic, where employees are characterized according to their gender. Women employees are overrepresented in a temporary tenure, thus at risk of losing jobs compared to men. It also added to their burden the flexible work which they have to keep balance between work and family while facing difficulties in playing the role [6]. Hence, the different agencies of government are tasked to act on this challenge to support and protect the rights of those employees experiencing gender characterization.

The Philippine Civil Service Commission Agenda on GAD expressed the thrust and directions under the CSC Performance Governance System (PGS) and Philippine Development Plan (PDP). It strongly encouraged the programs related to this approach wherein various policies and laws imposed such as the Philippine Plan for Gender-Responsive Development Plan (1995-2025), Women in Development and Nation Building Act (Republic Act No. 7192) and Anti-Sexual Harassment Act of 1995 (Republic Act No. 7877) (CSC Agenda, 2014). With this, different organizations especially the government strictly implemented this agenda to make sure that everyone has the equal opportunity and treatment in their workplace and most importantly the rights of the employees appertaining to them are exercised.

The Department of Education as the biggest agency of the government ensures that this is observed. The DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017 disseminated the utmost practice of gender-responsive basic education policy to strengthen it within the organization [7]. To value all concerned individuals in the department's umbrella, it rationalized that DepEd must adhere to this and should be timely tailored on the gender patterns in basic education indicators in the Philippines. This is to facilitate the teachers' sentiment on equality and the right to gain what they deserve in terms of opportunities.

The ASEAN Conference on Civil Service Matters (ACCSM) identified four areas where GAD could be applied among employees. These are recruitment and selection (This is searching for qualified candidates who meet the qualifications standards and undergo testing, interviewing and reference checking for selection); performance management (describes the practice that drives for decisions in remuneration, promotion, performance and etc.); rewards and recognition (valuing the contributions of the people in the organizations); and learning and development (enhancing people aligned to organization's objectives) [8].

These four areas are responsive to the needs of an individual, regardless of gender, to equal opportunity and equal treatment in the workplace. Furthermore, the public interest for transparency and just governance may prevail and no one is deprived to its rights as citizen who seeks employment, growth and belongingness. Gender is mainstreamed in the guidelines because it is definitely acknowledged the equal opportunity among individuals who are in the organization and the coming in employees.

An Equal Opportunity Framework can be a magnet for developing ideas in crafting GAD programs [9]. An example of program did by Kollmayer is the REFLECT. This approach was tailored on the systemic actiotope model that stimulated teachers' objective action repertoire and subjective action space which successfully resulted to the increase of gender fairness [10]. To reinforce more of the development, recommendations were pointed to have social networking among teachers. Mentoring activities or pairing teachers to work, building the chance for growth and increase opportunities to talk about context through sharing [11, 12].

As part of the development, an action plan is necessary to attain the goals. A framework made by Education International for the year 2016-2019, a gender equality action plan enabled the member organizations to employ the policies, rhetoric and activities related to gender. There were three main priorities on this action plan and these are promoting gender equality, securing girl's access and participation in quality public education and promoting and securing women's economic empowerment [13].

The present study sought the perceptions of teachers on gender and development based on the four areas identified by ASEAN Civil Service where the equal opportunity is also concerned. It tackled the experience of teachers regarding the importance of gender and development (GAD) practices in the school in terms of recruitment and selection, performance management, rewards and recognition, and learning and development. An action plan was developed to enrich GAD programs.

II. METHODS

A. Research Design and Setting

The study used the cross-sectional design to investigate the subjects through survey. Descriptive approach was used in this study. The study was conducted in a public high school which constitutes more than a thousand learners. The respondents of the study were forty teachers (no exclusion). Total population and purposive sampling was used. These teachers are holding full time work as classroom advisers, subject teachers, and teachers with special designation. The teachers are occupying position ranging from teacher I to master teacher II. Survey form was used at the same time short interview were conducted for the purpose of interpreting the responses made by the respondents.

B. Data Gathering

The tool used to gather data was validated then underwent an evaluation through pilot testing. After the process of validation and reliability test, writing a letter was done by the researcher to get the permission from the school principal to

allow the study to be conducted. For fast distribution and gathering of data, he prepared a hard copy survey. He scheduled the collection of data in second and third weeks of May. The distribution of survey form was done simultaneously while the researcher asked an informal mini-interview to the respondents. He was able to retrieve all the survey form before the estimated week allocated ended.

C. Survey Form

The survey form was used to gather the data. The survey form was a mixture of two sources and modified to suit to the respondents. The statements that are similar were merged to decrease the numbers of the statements, at the same time to consider the convenience of respondents. Basically, the form contains the four areas identified by the ACCSM and was combined with the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) handbook.

D. Reliability and Validity

In the pilot testing of the material, a Cronbach's Alpha was used for analysis to determine the reliability of the material which the internal consistency result is good (0.82). In the validity of the material used, this was anchored in a civil service commission handbook created under the ACCSM and National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA). Upon doing it, there were experts of panel in education checked and allowed to utilize the modified material.

E. Statistical Tool

The statistical tool used is basically descriptive statistics. For the data gathered, the statistical treatment used include mean and standard deviation. This treatment were used to interpret the data and describe it.

F. Ethical Consideration

The social science studies involving human participants require ethical standard on carrying out the study. In this research, starting from the crafting of the title down to the analysis and oral presentation were checked properly for ethical standard. The research panels made sure all of the necessary requirement had been done and discussed before the activity held especially the gathering of data.

As it was mentioned in the data gathering, this passed to legal process by which the school principal approval is necessary. It was explained of the purpose and the outcome benefit the teachers. Teachers-participants had been given the opportunity to understand the concept of study and given the choice to reject or participate. With due comprehension and consciousness, all teachers were affirmative in giving their time to take part in the study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Recruitment and Selection

The table 1 shows the teachers' interest in GAD practices to recruitment and selection. In the SD column, it can be observed that the statement 2 comes just next to statement 2,9 and 10. Looking at the statement 4 which has the lowest mean score has less scattered responses compared to statement 5 and 7. Meaning the distribution of responses are concentrated to a region. As overall impression, all the

responses of the respondents are concentrated almost to one place or region. This means that respondents are having the same outlook on these matters on recruitment and selection.

Hence, all means of the ten statements are described as very important.

Recruitment and Selection	Mean	SD *	DE *
1. Gender responsive objectives are clearly articulated in the policy on recruitment and selection.	4.78	0.42	Very Important
2. The implementing guidelines are gender responsive. (policy implementation)	4.83	0.38	Very Important
3. The policy consider and not discriminate pregnant women for appointment to government positions.	4.85	0.36	Very Important
4. There is a glaring disparity in the representation of men and women in the organization, is there a policy on affirmative action to correct it.	4.55	0.50	Very Important
5. The education, experience and training requirements are nondiscriminatory.	4.70	0.60	Very Important
6. The notice of vacancy adequately and timely disseminated internally and externally.	4.65	0.48	Very Important
7. The notice of vacancy explicitly encourage qualified men and women and people with disabilities to apply.	4.68	0.61	Very Important
8. Members of the selection committee required to undergo gender-sensitivity trainings.	4.80	0.40	Very Important
9. Gender and Development (GAD) focal person or GAD advocate part of the selection committee.	4.83	0.38	Very Important
10. There is a specific provision in the rules and regulations providing for inclusion of qualified women in the shortlist.	4.83	0.38	Very Important
Total	4.75	0.45	Very Important

Table 1: Teachers' interest in GAD practices to recruitment and selection.

Recruitment and selection is an important area of the civil service or the human resources to protect the right of every individual to be screened or under the process of selection without prejudices especially on gender. The respondents believed that gender responsive objectives must be clearly articulated in the organization policy so that all members of the recruitment and selection committee are oriented on the matter pertaining to this. The implementation guidelines should also be clearly seen without reservation. Applicants like pregnant women should also be entertained and has the right to advance in the higher position.

Representation of both men and women is there and when there is a disparity between, an immediate action must be done. The education or any background of respondents shouldn't be discriminated which respondents give high rate to this. It is also important that when informing people about the vacancy, it should be disseminated internally and externally but this gets small rate to the respondents.

For the people who have disabilities, it must be noticed that the no discrimination policy of physical appearance should be strictly followed. The members of selection should at least have trainings on the gender-responsive management so that they can fulfil at maximum their duty. It is encouraged that the focal person of GAD must sit as one of the selection committee member and make sure that the members abide the policy. Applicants especially women must know the rules and regulation for inclusion.

The human resource does their job professionally without the influence of prejudice and discrimination while respecting the different opinions among people has been reported not preserved including the national identity, gender and sexual orientation, discrimination against people with disabilities, political affiliation and age [14]. So this has a lot to say in the experience of applicants in the teaching profession and it showed the importance of the statements to

be highlighted or oriented to the selection and recruiting bodies particularly in the part of the principals. Gender stereotypes are avoided when there is a clear vision such like implementing policies or at least setting rules and regulation. Similar to classroom situation, mainstreaming the GAD in the classroom is a good approach to address gap and disparities among students [10]. The performance of the learners should not only be specified in one criteria just like the teachers when they are already in the school system. [10, 12, 13].

In DepEd, teachers believe that when this one is emphasized and implemented well, the upcoming school leaders will adapt to it and the recruitment and selection will be handled with utmost considerations.

B. Performance Management

Table 2 shows the teachers' interest in GAD practices to performance management.

The mean scores in all statements are high which can be interpreted as very important. When it comes to standard deviation of the statements how scattered the responses are, the distribution of responses is concentrated in an area. Therefore, the responses are near from one another. The statement that has closer responses is statement 5.

In this, the respondents agreed that in performance management to cater gender mainstreaming is very important. Provision of adjusting the work assignments and performance indicators in line with the welfare of the employees, gender-sensitive mechanism to guide and resolve any disagreement among the people in the organization, the competencies as indicators of performance are established to guide both the supervisor and the employees.

Moreover, gender-related outputs are required as part of the assessment and commitment. The policy is always there

to enforce the rights of employees especially women's privilege on maternity leave and other gender-related leaves. Transparency in assessing the performance should be objective so that everyone has equal footing in the performance regardless of the gender that the employees preferred.

A big no to sexual harassment to give safety to employees when at work, to enforce the no to sexual harassment environment is a guideline that should be clearly understood by the employees. An existing and operational grievance committee is present to facilitate any complaints. The work environment is good for everybody without triggering conflict among genders.

Performance Management	Mean	SD *	DE *
1. There is a provision to adjust work assignments and/or performance indicators in view of employee welfare concerns.	4.73	0.45	Very Important
2. There is a gender-sensitive mechanism to guide and resolve disagreement between supervisor and staff throughout the process.	4.83	0.38	Very Important
3. There are clear competency based development needs indicators established between employee and supervisor.	4.75	0.49	Very Important
4. Gender-related outputs and commitments are included in the performance commitment and assessed.	4.75	0.49	Very Important
5. There is a policy in place to ensure that employees on maternity leave and other gender-related leave will not be discriminated against in the assessment process.	4.90	0.30	Very Important
6. There is a gender-sensitive mechanism to ensure objectivity and transparency of assessment results.	4.80	0.41	Very Important
7. There is a policy that prevents sexual harassment (SH).	4.83	0.38	Very Important
8. Anti-sexual harassment policy and guidelines are known and understood by the employees.	4.80	0.46	Very Important
9. There is existing and operational grievance machinery.	4.78	0.48	Very Important
10. The work environment is safe and inclusive for women, men and people with disabilities.	4.88	0.33	Very Important
Total	4.81	0.42	Very Important

Table 2: Teachers' interest in GAD practices to performance management

It is suggested by experts that teachers or employees should be reinforced with guidance and support from colleague such as mentoring and helping one another. This shows no gap to people working in one environment which can make conduciveness to all [1, 12]. Both the top management and the lower level of employee will have connection that bond them and cut the edge of supremacy.

Teachers are aware and perceived the leadership of the principal, work environment and motivation to affiliate which directly influence their performance in the workplace. It was found out that teachers can perform well when the leadership of principal and the work environment are likely discerned. Furthermore, in motivation to affiliate does not really influence the performance of the teachers [15]. As it was mentioned how teachers agree to the statements, the policies, committees, programs and transparency are good to observe when dealing the performance of the teachers. When it comes to gender preference, refusal to maltreatment because of physical ability and capacity is discouraged to avoid double standard in rating employees for their performance. This related to the leadership ability and the kind of environment that teachers are in. This means that the performance of the teachers do not rely on themselves alone but the principal's influence and the conduciveness of work environment directly impact the performance. Moreover, this two direct influences have to see other factors that go behind this influence such as the roles of the top management, domestic condition of teachers, violence and sexual abuses, work burden, stress level and educational level [15].

Further, School leaders have to note that motivating people to cooperate with one another and help one another can be a big factor of success in the organization. Scholars believe that whenever sexual concerns arises, the organization should be responsive to address it and the top management is liable to investigate and solve the issue [12]. This is also to maintain harmonious environment and avoid the arising of potential similar issue in the workplace. In the DepEd system, this has been followed by the school leaders.

C. Rewards and Recognition

The table 3 shows the teachers' interest in GAD practices to rewards and recognition.

The standard deviation of the reward and recognition system show that the distribution concentrated in one place but not that definitely close. This means that some respondents rated the statements lower score how they perceived it.

The respondents believed that statements mentioned are very important which imposed that the organization should have clear set of criteria when it comes to rewards and recognition. This is crucial and all employees want it, everyone wants to be informed about the rewards and recognition.

It is the right of every individual to be informed. A provision of specific to pregnant women, employees on maternity leave and employees who have long term scholarship have perceived important to teachers. The

selection criteria are fair that no one feels discriminated nor unwelcome when filing the application for that purpose.

Moreover, initiatives of organization to mainstream the gender which compensate the efforts and initiatives done, should be enforced. Since women are disadvantaged most of the time an affirmative action to advance them is highly encouraged. The participation of women in the decision-making or vice versa should be recognized so as to initiate rewards to them.

Sex-disaggregated or the availability of gender related data must be available so that when possible of qualification and recognition the information is ready and fair, and most important to be agreed upon is that rewards and recognition is linked to the performance data from the employees.

It is positively agreed that in order to attain equitable environment for all employees, the organization initiates

change especially when the traditions which are biased do not give benefits to all the employees [5, 10]. The fact that rewards and recognition in global scenario impact the teachers' performance. This leads to positive impact and decrease the negative effect of work such as stress because of the rewards and recognition. It also a way of motivating employees [16]. Particularly in this matter is the male-dominated positions in an organization where it is perceived that male are given favor over women. So this tradition is desired to be changed to uplift and gain the trust of women by changing this image into equitable environment [17-18]. Perhaps the recognition and rewards system must be fair in the sense that no gender would feel behind or disadvantaged because of their preference. Hence, changing the bad tradition would change also the perception of disadvantaged group to believe that the workplace they are in are looking after for their benefits and interest [19, 20].

Rewards and Recognition	Mean	SD *	DE *
1. There are clear gender sensitive criteria for rewards and recognition.	4.80	0.46	Very Important
2. The rewards and recognition program is disseminated to all.	4.80	0.46	Very Important
3. There is a specific provision for pregnant women, employees on maternity leave, employee under long term scholarship to be considered for recognition.	4.80	0.40	Very Important
4. Selection criteria are fairly set so as not to discriminate against women who are pregnant or are on maternity leave/on long-term scholarship.	4.73	0.50	Very Important
5. There are initiatives to recognize gender mainstreaming efforts and initiatives.	4.73	0.50	Very Important
6. Given the prevailing context and circumstances of an organization, a temporary special measure is put in place as an affirmative action to advance the status and rights of women.	4.73	0.50	Very Important
7. Gender advocacy initiatives are rewarded and recognized such as agencies that promote women's participation in decision-making.	4.75	0.49	Very Important
8. Data on rewards and recognition are maintained.	4.73	0.45	Very Important
9. The data is sex-disaggregated or there is available gender related data on rewards and recognition.	4.65	0.66	Very Important
10. Performance data (e.g., ratings) is linked to rewards and recognition.	4.78	0.42	Very Important
Total	4.75	0.48	Very Important

Table 3: Teachers' interest in GAD practices to rewards and recognition

D. Learning and Development

Table 4 shows the teachers' interest in GAD practices to learning and development.

The mean scores of the statements are high which can be described as very important. Though comparing it with other tables in this part, this receives low rates in the high scale. In terms of distribution of responses as shown in the standard deviation, this shows concentration at one place, however, there is a distance where some respondents rated some statements lower.

To sum it up, respondents agreed that the statements have high importance on items in the learning and development are gender-sensitive. The learning gaps are anchored in the gender perspective through analysis. In designing methods, male and female capacities in using the technology are considered. Alternative way of delivering personal and professional needs of the individuals in their advancement must be appropriate and responsive.

Learning and Development	Mean	SD *	DE *
1. Questions/items in the Needs Analysis are gender sensitive.	4.68	0.52	Very Important
2. Learning gaps are generated analyzed from a gender perspective.	4.58	0.49	Very Important
3. In identifying methodology, instructional design considers the level of preparedness of women and men in the use of technologies.	4.78	0.42	Very Important
4. There are alternative modes of personal and professional advancement to ensure their gender appropriateness and responsiveness.	4.60	0.58	Very Important
5. Invitations specify gender balance in the number of participants to be sent.	4.68	0.57	Very Important
6. There is a policy to encourage women to attend trainings normally associated with men, such as leadership trainings.	4.75	0.49	Very Important

7. For gender trainings, it is emphasized that it is equally important for men to attend.	4.78	0.65	Very Important
8. The venue provides for practice of religious obligations.	4.63	0.58	Very Important
9. Resource speakers and facilitators use non-sexist language.	4.73	0.59	Very Important
10. Data on learning and development is maintained.	4.73	0.45	Very Important
Total	4.69	0.53	Very Important

Table 4. Teachers' interest in GAD practices to learning and development

Furthermore, when there is an invitation for training and opportunities then an equal number or justified number among gender or sex are fair when sending delegates. Women are encouraged to attend training that men usually are associated with just like leadership. Men are encouraged to attend gender trainings, that the venues are open for religious obligation for those employees would practice their faith during training. The resource speakers of training use fair language which is not offensive to any gender, and the data on learning and development is maintained.

There are notions mentioned about the support of the organization to productively meet the requirement on efficient and effective implementation on gender and development, the support must come from the top management. To make sure it will be established properly, the budget allocated on GAD must be used to carry out the different activities like learning and development of teachers [21, 22]. The learning and development opportunities among countries vary, however, it is a concern that when some teachers receive none on the professional development then this calls for a problem to look into. It was reported that teachers want more professional development and it was found out that women especially at the middle age employees in public schools received minimal opportunity and thus expressed unsatisfied with the learning and development [24]. Importance of having fair division of opportunities across all ages and genders matter and this is why respondents of this study expressed the importance of the implementation and equal distribution of opportunities to teachers.

An important note to remember in doing this is the impact that can give to both male and female employees. If not, it will be turn to nothing the plans for teachers in which a researcher discussed in his research the failure of GAD in some universities in a certain region in the Philippines [20]. In one way or another, the drive to succeed in maintaining GAD in the atmosphere of school is the cooperation between the involved people especially the top management and the employees.

Talon and his colleagues clearly said that in application those aspects (learning and development) in the class where the students are the benefactors of teachers' training [4]. It is good in strengthening the personnel background and orientation regarding the gender issues and concerns to deeply absorb the purpose of the vital importance of GAD within the circle as well as outside the circle group of the teachers [5, 16, 17]. This simply emphasized in developing professional growth among teachers, it is said that social networking is good for teachers especially when they are in a place where the culture is different from them [1, 16].

So this is even true in the Philippines where teachers adjust to the kind of community where the students are coming from. Letting the teachers exchange ideas in order to come up with a better strategy to increase the opportunity of reaching their target and to become effective in their work. More than this, they build good relationship to diverse of people not only student but also to different stakeholders [24].

E. Action Plan

The results of all four areas mentioned are very important. The programs in the action plan consists of different activities that can be conducted in different time in an academic year. Since every concepts in the various areas were very important, the design of the plan to be implemented is anchored in each areas and its contents.

A contextualized made program called REFLECT which boost teachers to put into action their plans is antecedent to gender development. Its primary goal is to give equality among colleagues in the workplace [10]. This comes to realization that in order to motivate the employees particularly the teachers a program that would be implemented must have sustainability. It also gives support to teachers for them to unleash their potentials and improve just like the others regardless of gender or sex role. Moreover, if there will be a movement of principals then the implementation and practice of GAD activities cannot be automatically affected by new principal coming in.

Since this study was conducted in one school, this might not be true to other school. Therefore, the adaption and application of the action plan may vary. This should be validated according to the context. The assurance that this plan gave is the protection and consideration of the gender related issues in the school as it is being addressed.

IV. CONCLUSION

Mainstreaming gender in the programs of school has brought improvement to the welfare of all employees by exercising their rights as individual and a part of the organization where they serve. In the recruitment and selection, there is high in need of checking the process of hiring and selecting candidates that fit to the organization regardless of the gender, nationality, disabilities, political affiliation and religion. This is practice of equal opportunities. However, in the current practices, maintaining this equality is a challenged to organizations. For the performance management, the principal and work environment is deeply influential in the total performance of individuals. This is how important that administrators should take into reflection. The rewards and recognition is a best way to express appreciation and value the employees contributed to the organization whether big or small. This is

also a source of motivation to keep men and women work harder. For learning and development, it is noteworthy that the obligation of the top management is also to function as mover of the GAD programs for the personal growth of the employees at the same time gaining professional development as they stay in the organization. Sometimes, the main problem is losing the potentials teachers to exert efforts and instead of growing as an asset of the organization, they become passive. This has also something to do with being stagnant if ever the school leaders do not see the progress of their colleague.

In adherence to the utmost practice of GAD in educational institutions, this study recommends specific unit in the organization: the human resource unit. However, this does not assure its effectiveness since this was tested in one school only. With this, it is a job of the HR person to see how the mandates of the agency appear to be effective in the workplace. Therefore, to deeply analyze the condition of employee, studying gender related issue would give hint to the creation of new strategy to motivate the employees to become passionate and activated.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher expresses his gratitude to the positive response of the school principal of the subject school. Of equal recognition is expressed to the teachers who were kind to participate and spare their precious time to help the researcher successfully conducted the study accordingly. Sincerest gratitude is given to the two anonymous reviewers, for their comments and suggestions which greatly improved this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Department of Science and Technology Philippine Science High School Zamboanga Peninsula Region Campus. Available online: <https://zrc.pshs.edu.ph/gender-and-development-gad-corner/>(accessed on 20 November 2021).
- [2.] Badri, M.; Alnuaimi, A.; Muhaidat, J.; Yang, G.; Al Rashedi, A. Perception of teachers' professional development needs, impacts, and barriers: The Abu Dhabi case. *SAGE Open*. 2016, 6.
- [3.] Burakgazi, S. G.; Can, I.; Coşkun, M. Exploring pre-service teachers' perceptions about professional ethics in teaching: Do gender, major, and academic achievement matter?. *IJPE* 2020. 16.
- [4.] Department of Education (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017) Available online: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/06/29/do-32-s-2017-gender-responsive-basic-education-policy/> (accessed on 27 February 2021).
- [5.] Moses, I.; Admiraal, W.; Berry, A. Gender and gender role differences in student-teachers' commitment to teaching. *Soc Psychol Educ* 2016. 19, 475-492.
- [6.] International Labor Organization. Available online: [https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_700953/lang--en/index .htm](https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_700953/lang--en/index.htm). (accessed on 20 November 2021).
- [7.] Battley, D.; Kafai, Y.; Nixon, A. S.; Kao, L. Professional Development for teachers on gender equity in the sciences: Initiating the conversation. *Teachers College Record*, Columbia University 2007. 109.
- [8.] Association of Southeast Asian Nations & Philippine Civil Service Commission. Gender mainstreaming in human resource policies, processes and systems A training manual. 2015.
- [9.] Talon, R.; Carreon, J.; Diragen, G. A phenomenological inquiry of gender and development in the classroom program. 2020.
- [10.] Kollmayer, M.; Schultes, M.; Lüftenegger, M.; Finsterwald, M.; Spiel, C.; Schober, B. REFLECT-A teacher training program to promote gender equality in schools. *Front. Educ.* 2020. 5.
- [11.] Reeves, H.; Baden, S. Gender and Development: Concepts and definitions. BRIDGE (Development-Gender). Institute of Development Studies, University of Sussex, 2000.
- [12.] Learning Policy Institute. Available online: <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/effective-teacher-professional-development-report> (accessed on 28 February 2021)
- [13.] McNamara, P.; Geary, T.; Jourdan, D. Gender implications of the teaching of relationships and sexuality education for health-promoting schools. *Health Promotion International* 2010. 26.
- [14.] Education International. Available online: https://download.ei-ie.org/Docs/WebDepot/EI_GEAP_2015_ENG_web.pdf (accessed on 20 November 2021)
- [15.] Stoilkovska, A; Ilieva, J.; Gjakovski, S. Equal employment opportunities in the recruitment and selection process of human resources. *UTMS Journal of Economics* 2015, 6, 281–292.
- [16.] Hartinaha, S.; Suharsob, P.; Umamc, R.; Syazalid, M.; Dwi Lestari, B.; Roslinae, R.; Jermstiparsertf. K. Teacher's performance management: The role of principal's leadership, work environment and motivation in Tegal City, Indonesia. *Management Science Letters* 2019, 10, 235–246. Hussain, S. D.; Khaliq, D. A.; Nisar, Q. A.; Kamboh, A. Z.; Ali, S. Impact of employees' recognition, rewards and job stress on job performance: Mediating role of perceived organization support. *Strategic Management Journal* 2019, 2, 69-82.
- [17.] Pulmano, R. Implementation of the gender and development program of state universities and colleges in Region III: An evaluation. *International Journal of Education and Research* 2016, 4.
- [18.] Staib, K. Constructivist theory and overcoming the gender gap in education in Latin America. *Sigma: Journal of Political and International Studies* 2012, 29.
- [19.] Zosuls, K.; Miller, C.; Ruble, D.; Martin, C.; Fabes, R. Gender development research in sex roles: Historical trends and future directions. *National Institute of Health* 2005.
- [20.] Valencia, M. I. Gender mainstreaming in teacher education institution in the Philippines. *EDUCARE: IJES* 2017, 9, 85-94.

- [21.] Perigo, M.; Mangila, B. Extent of implementation of the gender and development program in a state college of the Philippines. APJMR 2020, 8.
- [22.] Amadi, E. Introduction to educational administration: A module. Harey Publications, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. 2008.
- [23.] Asante, E. Gender and development theory, policy and practice through a feminist postmodern lens: A case study of CIDA's policies on women 1995-2000. National Library of Canada, Canada. TALIS. 2019, 47-86.